

HOW TO TEACH LITERARY ELEMENTS IN THE HIGHER EDUCATIONAL UNIVERSITY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6528515>

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Abstract: *Key features of literary elements are explained by this article. And the reader easily understand that the literary elements are writing techniques used to deeply engage the reader in the text. These elements are also used by authors to explore the artistry of language.*

Key words: *literary element, concrete definitions, Bloom's taxonomy, comprehension, indirect characterization*

Introfuction

A **literary element**, or **narrative element**, or **element of literature** is an essential characteristic of all works of written and spoken [narrative fiction](#). Literary elements include [plot](#), [theme](#), [character](#) and [tone](#). In contrast, [literary techniques](#) are non-universal features of literature and include [figurative language](#), [irony](#), and [foreshadowing](#). Literary elements aid in the discussion of and understanding of a work of literature as basic categories of critical analysis; literary elements could be said to be produced by the readers of a work just as much as they are produced by its author. For the most part, they are popular concepts that are not limited to any particular branch of [literary criticism](#), although they are most closely associated with the [formalist method](#) of professional literary criticism. There is no official definition or fixed list of terms of literary elements; however, they are a common feature of literary education at the [primary](#) and [secondary](#) level, and a set of terms similar to the one below often appears in institutional student evaluation. For instance, the New York State Comprehensive English [Regents Exam](#) requires that students use and discuss literary elements relating to specific works in each of the three essays

Understanding literary elements is a complex process that encourages students to develop skills existing at several levels of Bloom's taxonomy. For this reason, teachers have a wonderful opportunity to scaffold learning experiences using literary elements when teaching fiction. By teaching students to own their

knowledge of literary elements, teachers are helping them build a solid foundation of analytical thinking skills.

Discussion

Defining Literary Elements

Analyzing literature first requires students to understand a variety of literary terms and definitions. Just like a handyman carries around his trusty tool bag, literature students must fill up their own resource sack before getting down to the challenging work of analysis. Therefore, they must know the concrete definitions to an array of literary terms. Be sure to provide students with a [comprehensive list of terms](#) they will be expected to know or learn throughout the school year.

Applying Literary Elements

It's important that teachers start out by explaining to students that literary elements are tools that will help them access literature for the rest of their lives. These are terms and concepts that they need to not only thoroughly understand, but also to use and apply to different texts as they progress through high school and college.

Analysis Enhances Comprehension

Consider Sir Arthur Conan Doyle's *The Hound of the Baskervilles*, a famous Sherlock Holmes tale. This can be a dense text for students to comprehend and, although they are likely to enjoy the suspenseful plot, they may not connect with the language. But when students apply their knowledge of literary elements to such as text, they can more deeply connect with the story, identify the characters, and uncover timeless themes still relevant in today's society. They will start to realize that [analysis](#) improves comprehension, and in return comprehension improves analysis. But they must be heartily supported to get there.

Scaffolding Analysis

Ideally, teachers will scaffold the use of sophisticated literary elements in the upper grades with the more concrete, easily understood terms in the lower grades such as

- indirect characterization
- direct characterization
- plot
- external conflict
- internal conflict

Literary Elements Diagnostic Testing

One way to ensure your students are mostly on the same page is to administer a diagnostic test assessing their current knowledge of literary elements. You may

not be as successful using dictionary definitions here; instead, try incorporating examples into your questions. This way, you are more likely to uncover what students really know but haven't necessarily memorized.

Sample Questions

Here are two sample questions that illustrate the idea that comprehension enhances analysis.

1. Who is being described in the following quote?

“ . . . he had contrived, with that catlike love of personal cleanliness which was one of his characteristics, that his chin should be as smooth and his linen as perfect as if he were in Baker Street” (178).

A. Dr. Watson

B. Mr. Barrymore

C. Sherlock Holmes

D. Mr. Frankland

2. In the above quote, what literary element is being applied?

A. Personification

B. Simile

C. Direct characterization

D. Indirect characterization

Throughout your course, you can easily take this discussion further by asking more thought-provoking questions, such as

- Why does Doyle use direct characterization at some points in the novel and indirect characterization at others?

- How is the character indirectly revealed throughout the course of the novel? Consider both the character's speech and actions.

- Which method of characterization is more effective when revealing complex characters? Cite examples from the text to support your position.

Conclusion

Encourage students to see the many benefits of understanding and actively considering the function of literary elements when they read fiction. The ultimate goal, of course, is for students to apply their knowledge of literary elements to help assess and respond to a variety of texts with relative comfort and a degree of authority.

Through literary elements, you can draw the reader into your story, and encourage them to engage with the text. Literary devices can stimulate the reader's mind, and giving them a deeper reading experience. Make your writing more interesting to read. Learning literary elements will enable a reader to understand

the underlying structure of the texts. Literary figures are the elements that constitute the whole body of a given sentence. Thus, the meaning of a sentence will vary according to the use of literary elements. For example- He got the wheel means he got the vehicle and wheel metonymically refers the vehicle. The structure of writing depends on literary elements and therefore the meaning it conveys will depend on those elements.

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